
**ANALYSIS OF THE WORKS OF JADID LITERATURE IN THE
RESEARCH OF INGEBORG BALDAUF**

Sadullayeva Dilnoza Nortozi's daughter

**Base doctoral student of the National University of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulugbek**

Annotation: In this article I. Baldauf's research on Uzbek jadid literature was analyzed. In particular, the analysis of the works of Fitrat was considered from the point of view of the scientist. It was noted that Baldauf was able to analyze the works by reading them fluently in the Uzbek language, as well as the connection he had established with Uzbek writers and readers. Records have been cited that Ingeborg Baldauf translated Fitrat's works into German and published them with commentaries.

Keywords: drama, research, art, theater.

With the fact that Jadid literature shows marriage realistically and vividly, raises irreplaceable topics, necessary national attitudes, our nation occupies a great place in the development of the word art. Much research has been done in our literary studies on the peculiarities of this period. O. In Uzbekistan. Sharafiddinov, N. Karimov, B. Kasimov, H. Boltaboyev, B. Dostqorayev, N. Vlademirovna, I. Ganiyev, U. Jo ' studied by Raqulov and other scientists.

20th century Uzbek jadid literature has been consistently studied and researched not only in our country, but also abroad. Studied abroad by researchers such as Edward Allworth, Elen de Enkaus, Ingeborg Baldauf, Hisao Komatsu, son of Temur Hoja, Yusuf Awji. When it comes to the research of scientists, the famous German scientist I. We cannot stop at Baldauf separately. Olima's collection "drawings on Uzbek literature of the 20th century" is devoted to the history of Turkestan jadidism and the work of its famous exponents. This collection is sorted by Ingeborg Baldauf's views on Fitrat, Behbudi, Kadiri, Chulpan. The opinions and opinions of a foreign Specialist are interesting not only for our science of literary

studies, but also for readers. I. Baldauf was fluent in Uzbek. Our writers thought by reading their works in Uzbek from originals. Whether he discusses behbudi, mentions Avloni, talks about Munavvarqori with high respect for the personality and creativity of all of them. He studies old Arabic script to read works in Uzbek. Another notable aspect is that whatever fact he refers to in his research, characterizing some event makes it clear where this information is given, which text it is based on. In his works, dates, names of Works, place names, people were studied with extreme attention, repeatedly examined. The requirements of genuine science are embodied in the scientist. The love of the German scientist for Uzbekistan is such that the year visits our country, talks with Uzbek readers, researchers for the reason of the symposium, conferences, shares its thoughts. He visits ancient settlements such as Samarkand and Bukhara. Interest in the opinion of Uzbek readers, at the same time sharing their plans, we will not be mistaken to say the peculiarity of Baldauf. His friendship with Uzbek intellectuals deserves special mention. His research on the manifestations of Uzbek jadid literature also serves as an excellent resource for current readers.

The German nobleman Ingeborg Baldauf, in many of his studies, described the life of Turkestan and Bukhara at the beginning of the 20th century as described by Professor Hamidulla Boltaboyev in his book "Fitrat and jadidism". In his article "some reflections on the formation of the Uzbek Nation", published in the complex "correspondence on the Russian and Soviet peoples", Baldauf draws attention to the delimitation of the national state and its consequences in Central Asia in the 20s. "Sart", "muslim", "chigatoy", "Turkish", referring to the Uzbek nation, expound their reflections on the genesis of their reforms and the history of their application in scientific circulation. Baldauf was said to be the most prominent Fitrat among the jadis of Central Asia. In Fitrat's "debate", he quotes "the result of truth is coincidence afkor ast", i.e., "diversity of thoughts makes sense of reality", and argues that Fitrat has lived his entire life looking for truth, not limited to just saying slogans in the process of diversity of thoughts, contradictions, but that reality has achieved such a level in moderation that not a middle Asian Thinker has reached this

level. Fitrat fully agrees with the Jadid demand that “truth should be at the disposal” in one faranggi ila Bukharan Mudarris ' qilghan debate on jadid schools, published in Istanbul in 1911, and in favor of the truth favored by his fellow jadid thinkers. The European in the “debate” is Fitrat himself. Baldauf says that at the heart of Fitrat's works “Me'roj”, “Zahro's faith”, “Zayd and Zaynab” is not the “truth” itself, but the subjective attitude of people towards reality. Baldauf says that about Fitrat “brilliant figure of a group of intellectual figures active during the years of the revolution in Central Asia, who remained in arosat between politics and culture and enlightenment, Fitrat famous, who received a more detailed and deeper Oriental Education than the enlighteners, considered by the way of life, spirituality of Islam and Central Asia, professed unprecedented deep and broad opinions in jadidism. “His works on religion and faith are of particular importance. They show the path that the Thinker has taken. Fitrat defends the jadidism that is passing through his cloister: The Fanatic sees him as writing a “debate” against priests and religious officials. Ingeborg published Baldauf Fitrat's poetic drama “The Rebellion of Satan to the Tang” in German, with commentary. Referring to Fitrat's 1924 drama “Satan's rebellion to the tang”, he states that the drama did not receive sufficient attention from both literary scholars and theologians.

This is due to the fact that the play has few copies and is difficult to find in libraries. The greater the philosophical level of the work in the literary criterion, the less its influence on the process of artistic thinking, and the reason why the work is not put on stage, first of all, is due to the essence of the work, socio-political phenomena are also caused. A complete ode to the theater, where modernity entered its scenes, was the “Rebellion of Satan to the Tang”. Fitrat never claimed dramaturgy, his work modernity. Despite the publication of the work, the disapproval of the Uzbek literary environment is attributed to the fact that it fell off the stage without contributing to the development of the Uzbek theater. Of the work, Baldauf says: ““the Rebellion of Satan to the Tang” was designed to be a reading pleasure of a circle of a narrow intellectual, rather than a stage play intended for the general public”. In modern Eastern literature, there seems to be no work similar to

the drama “Satan's rebellion against tangry”, created by Fitrat. As philosophy and literature in Central Asia became increasingly isolated from the Islamic world, it says that there were no followers of the “Rebellion of Satan to the Tang”. The work says that in the work of Fitrat, perhaps, as the only peak in Uzbek literature in general, he still lives secluded to this day. Olima's reflections on the formation of the Uzbek nation are extremely noteworthy that olima deeply examines the roots of events that led to the next eighty years of changes of the Uzbek people. Behbudi, who had already seen these “changes” in his time, explores the work of scholars and poet such as Fitrat not from a reformist point of view, but from the point of view of the people and the future of the nation, and from the point of view of the heroes of the nation who fought for the nation not to come to such Baldauf's love for his work and love for Uzbek jadid literature are evident in his scientific research. And the fact that every work and creator is respected is admirable.

Jadid literature in particular, since the literary and political activities of Fitrat are widely and deeply studied by foreign scholars, we should go into a deep study of the scientific and literary activities of the scientist. I believe that we should promote to the people in the learning drum.

List of literature used:

1. Begali Kasimov. Maslakdosh.- T.: East, 1994.
2. Boltaboyev H. Fitrat and jadidism. - T.: A.Publishing house of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Navoi, 2007.
3. Ingeborg Baldauf. Drawings on Uzbek literature of the XX century. - T.: Spirituality, 2001.
4. Zulkhumor Mirzayeva. The study of Uzbek literature of the 20th century in America. - T.: Science, 2011.